

Status of Some Haematological and Biochemical Parameters in Patients Diagnosed with Chronic Kidney Disease at Imo State Specialist Hospital, Umuguma, Owerri, Nigeria

Nwaozor Chidimma M¹., Aloy-Amadi Oluchi C¹., Nwabueze Jennifer U¹., Emeka - Obi Obioma R²., Akogu Okechukwu³, Ezeh Caleb C⁴. and ¹Nnodim Johnkennedy

¹Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria.

²Department of Haematology, College of Medicine, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.

³Department of Optometry, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Haematology, Federal Teaching Hospital, Owerri, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: [Aloy-Amadi Oluchi C.](#)

Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria.

Abstract

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a prevalent global health challenge characterized by the progressive deterioration of renal function leading to significant metabolic, haematological, and cardiovascular complications. This study was aimed at evaluating the levels of red cell distribution width (RDW), mean platelet volume (MPV), white blood cell (WBC), serum creatinine, urea and albumin in patients with chronic kidney disease at Imo State Specialist Hospital, Umuguma, Owerri, Nigeria. A total of sixty (60) subjects were enrolled in the study and consisted of thirty (30) patients with chronic kidney disease and 30 age-matched apparently healthy subjects (controls). Ethical approval and informed consent were obtained from the ethics committee of the hospital and subjects respectively. Venous blood (7mls) was collected from the patients by venipuncture using sterile needles and syringes and dispensed into plain tubes (5mls) and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) containers (2mls) immediately. The non-haemolysed samples in the plain tubes were centrifuged and separated and the serum samples were stored at -20°C prior to use, while the blood in the EDTA container was stored in the refrigerator at 4 °C. All reagents were commercially procured and the manufacturer's standard operating procedures were strictly followed. Serum creatinine was determined using the Jaffe-Slot method, urea was determined using the diacetyl monoxime method, MPV and RDW and WBC were determined using haematology autoanalyser (Sysmex KX2IN while serum albumin was determined using the Bromocresol Green method. Values were presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD) and $p < 0.05$ level of significance was adopted. All data obtained in the study were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 21). The mean values of urea (62.77 ± 38.59)mg/dl, creatinine (2.72 ± 2.27)mg/dl, RDW (52.12 ± 8.42)fl, MPV (11.05 ± 1.59)fl, WBC (10.25 ± 4.02) cells/l were significantly in chronic kidney disease patients when compared to controls (18.10 ± 6.08)mg/dl, (0.66 ± 0.31)mg/dl, (43.46 ± 8.97)fl, (8.63 ± 0.93)fl and (5823.33 ± 1969.89) cells/ul respectively ($P = 0.000$) while albumin (3.34 ± 0.93)mg/dl, was significantly lower when compared to controls (4.50 ± 0.86)mg/dl ($P = 0.000$). There was no significant difference in the mean values of urea (63.40 ± 42.95)mg/dl, creatinine (3.09 ± 2.85)mg/dl, albumin (3.05 ± 0.77)mg/dl, RDW (52.11 ± 6.78)fl, MPV (10.94 ± 1.78)fl and WBC (10.40 ± 4.59) cells/ul in males with chronic kidney disease when compared to that of the females (62.13 ± 35.19)mg/dl, (2.34 ± 1.49)mg/dl, (3.63 ± 0.99)mg/dl, (52.13 ± 10.04)fl, (11.17 ± 1.44)fl and (10.09 ± 3.52) cells/ul. There was no significant difference in the mean values of urea, creatinine, albumin, RDW, MPV and WBC in patients with chronic kidney disease when compared based on gender and age. There was a significant positive correlation of serum creatinine with urea in patients with chronic kidney disease ($r = 0.64$, $p = 0.000$). There was a non-significant positive correlation of serum creatinine with albumin, RDW, MPV and WBC in patients with chronic kidney disease ($r = 0.08$, $p = 0.683$; $r = 0.23$, $p = 0.228$; $r = 0.05$, $p = 0.808$ and $r = 0.38$, $p = 0.039$). Chronic kidney disease is associated with elevated levels of urea, creatinine, RDW, MPV, WBC and a significant decrease in albumin. Gender and age do not affect the levels of urea, creatinine, albumin, RDW, MPV and WBC in patients with chronic kidney disease. Therefore, we recommend that routine assessment of urea and creatinine should remain the cornerstone of CKD diagnosis and progression monitoring, and MPV, RDW and WBC should be assessed as part of cardiovascular risk evaluation, in routine blood tests for CKD patients to evaluate anaemia severity, and to detect systemic inflammation and its potential role in exacerbating CKD-related complications respectively.

Keywords: Urea, Creatinine, Mean Platelet Volume, Red Cell Distribution Width, White Blood Cell, Chronic Kidney Disease.

1. Introduction

Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is a growing global health concern, characterized by progressive loss of kidney function over a period of months to years. Early identification and management are crucial to slowing the disease progression and preventing complications, such as end-stage renal disease. A comprehensive understanding of biomarkers and laboratory parameters associated with CKD is essential for both diagnosis and monitoring. Various hematological and biochemical markers, including white blood cell count (WBC), mean platelet volume (MPV), red cell distribution width (RDW), urea, creatinine, and albumin, are increasingly being investigated for their potential role in assessing disease severity and prognosis in CKD patients.

White Blood Cell Count (WBC) plays a pivotal role in the immune response and has been shown to increase in chronic inflammatory conditions like CKD. Elevated WBC counts are often associated with systemic inflammation and endothelial dysfunction, which contribute to the cardiovascular morbidity observed in CKD patients (Shah, 2015). Moreover, increased WBC levels may reflect an exacerbation of kidney injury or the presence of comorbidities such as diabetes or hypertension, which are common among CKD patients (Kovacs et al., 2013).

Mean Platelet Volume (MPV) is a measure of platelet size, and an increase in MPV has been linked to platelet activation and a prothrombotic state. Research suggests that higher MPV levels are associated with adverse cardiovascular outcomes in CKD patients (Demir et al., 2016). MPV, alongside other platelet indices, may provide useful insight into the degree of platelet activation and its relationship with disease progression (Gupta et al., 2014).

Red Cell Distribution Width (RDW) is a measure of the variation in the size of red blood cells. An elevated RDW has been identified as an independent risk factor for mortality in CKD patients, reflecting the underlying pathophysiology of anemia associated with CKD, including iron deficiency, inflammation, and erythropoietin resistance (Tanaka et al., 2013). RDW is thought to provide additional prognostic value in CKD, particularly when combined with other markers such as hemoglobin levels and ferritin (Alvarez et al., 2019).

Urea and Creatinine are classic markers of kidney function. Elevated levels of urea and creatinine are typically indicative of impaired glomerular filtration rate (GFR), which is the hallmark of CKD (Levey et al., 2015). Urea, often used alongside creatinine, provides complementary information on renal function, with urea levels affected by factors such as protein intake, hydration, and liver function (Ninomiya et al., 2012).

Albumin is a key protein in the blood plasma that serves a variety of functions, including maintaining oncotic pressure and transporting various molecules. Hypoalbuminemia, a common finding in CKD, is associated with increased risk of complications, including cardiovascular events, infections, and mortality. The degree of albuminuria (albumin excretion in the urine) is also a key marker of CKD progression (Catran et al., 2013). Albumin levels, in conjunction with other markers, offer critical prognostic information in CKD patients.

This study on the interplay between these biomarkers and their clinical significance in CKD is essential for improving patient care and outcomes. The following review examines the status of WBC, MPV, RDW, urea, creatinine, and albumin in CKD patients, with a focus on their diagnostic and prognostic value in the management of this chronic disease.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Site

The study was conducted at the Imo State Specialist Hospital, Umuguma, Owerri, Nigeria.

2.2 Study Design

A cross-sectional study was conducted from the month of June to September, 2023 and all eligible subjects (30 patients and 30 apparently healthy subjects) were enrolled in the study. Blood samples were collected and analyzed in the laboratory using standard operating procedures. The results of the tests were analyzed using SPSS version 21.

2.3 Method of Recruitment

The study consisted of adult chronic kidney diseased patients attending Imo specialist hospital, Umuguma, Owerri, Nigeria. A total of sixty subjects (30 patients and 30 age-matched healthy subjects) who gave their informed consent and completed the questionnaire were enrolled in the study.

2.4 Ethical Consideration

This research study was approved by the ethics and research committee of Imo specialist hospital, Umuguma, Owerri. All study participants who gave their informed consent were enrolled in this study and samples were taken.

2.5 Selection criteria

2.5.1 Inclusion criteria

Patients suffering from chronic kidney disease without any other medical conditions (in the age range of 30-65years)

Patients who gave their informed consent.

Age-matched apparently healthy subjects who served as controls.

2.5.2 Exclusion criteria

- i. Patients who did not give their informed consent.
- ii. Patients below and above the ages of 30-65years
- iii. Patients with other medical conditions like urinary tract infections, evidence of urological disease and evidence of heart failure.

2.6 Sample Collection

Venous blood (7mls) were collected from the patients by venipuncture using sterile needles and syringes. 5 mls of blood was dispensed into plain containers and used for the estimation of serum creatinine, urea and albumin, while 2mls was dispensed EDTA containers and used for the determination of WBC, MPV and RDW. The non-haemolysed samples in the plain tubes were centrifuged and separated and the serum samples were stored at -20°C prior to use, while the blood in the EDTA container was stored in the refrigerator at 4°C .

2.8 Laboratory Analysis

The WBC, Mean Platelet Volume and Red Cell Distribution Width were estimated using Using haematology autoanalyser (Sysmex KX2IN). The Jaffe-Slot method was used to determine serum creatinine (test kit from Randox (Catalogue No: Cr12245370). Serum urea was estimated using Diacetyl monoxime method – urea assay kit (Catalogue Number: MAK006). The determination of serum albumin was done using the Bromocresol Green method, using Randox Albumin Assay-AL145.

3. Statistical Analysis

All data obtained in the study was analyzed using student t-test (SPSS 21) and Pearson correlation coefficient. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Values were expressed as mean \pm SD and results presented in tables.

4. Results

Table 1: Mean Values of Urea, Creatinine, Albumin in patients with chronic kidney disease compared to Controls.

The mean value of urea (62.77 ± 38.59) mg/dl was significantly higher in patients suffering from chronic kidney disease when compared to controls (18.10 ± 6.08) mg/dl ($t=6.26$, $P=0.000$).

The mean value of creatinine (2.72 ± 2.27)mg/dl was significantly higher in patients suffering from chronic kidney disease when compared to controls (0.66 ± 0.31)mg/dl. ($t=4.92$, $P=0.000$), while serum albumin (3.34 ± 0.93)mg/dl was significantly lower in subjects suffering from chronic kidney disease when compared to controls (4.50 ± 0.86) mg/dl ($t=5.01$, $P=0.000$).

Parameter	Test	Control	t-value	p-value
Urea (mg/dl)	62.77 ± 38.59	18.10 ± 6.08	6.26	0.000*
Creatinine (mg/dl)	2.72 ± 2.27	0.66 ± 0.31	4.92	0.000*
Albumin (mg/dl)	3.34 ± 0.93	4.50 ± 0.86	5.01	0.000*

Table 2: Mean Values of RDW, MPV, and WBC in Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease compared to controls.

The mean values of RDW (52.12 ± 8.42)fl and MPV (11.05 ± 1.59)fl were significantly higher in patients suffering from chronic kidney disease when compared to controls (43.46 ± 8.97) fL and (8.63 ± 0.93) fl respectively.

Similarly, WBC (10.25 ± 4.02) cells/ μl was significantly raised in patients suffering from chronic kidney disease when compared to controls (5.82 ± 2.00)cells/ μl .

Parameter	Test	Control	t-value	p-value
RDW (fL)	52.12 ± 8.42	43.46 ± 8.97	3.85	0.000*
MPV (fl)	11.05 ± 1.59	8.63 ± 0.93	7.19	0.000*

WBC (cells/ μ l)	10.25 \pm 4.02	5.82 \pm 2.00	5.41	0.000*
----------------------	------------------	-----------------	------	--------

KEY:

* = Significant p value

RDW= Red Cell Distribution Width

MPV= Mean Platelet Volume

WBC= White Blood Cell

Table 3: Comparison of the Mean Values of Urea, Creatinine, Albumin, RDW, MPV and WBC in Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease based on Gender.

There was no significant difference in the mean values of urea (63.40 \pm 42.95)mg/dl, creatinine (3.09 \pm 2.85)mg/dl, albumin (3.05 \pm 0.77)mg/dl, RDW(52.11 \pm 6.78)fl, MPV (10.94 \pm 1.78)fl and WBC (10.40 \pm 4.59) cells/ μ l in males with chronic kidney disease when compared to the mean values of urea (62.13 \pm 35.19)mg/dl, creatinine (2.34 \pm 1.49)mg/dl, albumin (3.63 \pm 0.99)mg/dl, RDW (52.13 \pm 10.04) fl, MPV (11.17 \pm 1.44) fl and WBC (10.09 \pm 3.52) cells/ μ l in females with chronic kidney disease (t= 0.09, P= 0.930), (t=0.91,P=0.372), (t=1.78, P=0.086) (T=0.01,p=0.997), (t= 0.38, P=0.704) and (t= 0.21, P=0.839).

Parameter	Male 15	Female 15	t-value	p-value
Urea (mg/dl)	63.40 \pm 42.95	62.13 \pm 35.19	0.09	0.930
Creatinine (mg/dl)	3.09 \pm 2.85	2.34 \pm 1.49	0.91	0.372
Albumin (mg/dl)	3.05 \pm 0.77	3.63 \pm 0.99	1.78	0.086
RDW (fL)	52.11 \pm 6.78	52.13 \pm 10.04	0.01	0.997
MPV (fl)	10.94 \pm 1.78	11.17 \pm 1.44	0.38	0.704
WBC (cells/ μ l)	10.40 \pm 4.59	10.09 \pm 3.52	0.21	0.839

KEY:

RDW= Red Cell distribution width

MPV= Mean platelet Volume

WBC= White blood cell

Table 4: Comparison of the Mean Values of Urea, Creatinine, Albumin, RDW, MPV and WBC in Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease based on Age.

There were no significant difference in the mean values of Urea: 30-40 yrs (60.00 \pm 24.76), 41-50(65.13 \pm 33.87) and > 50yrs (64.33 \pm 43.59) (f= 0.02, p= 0.981); creatinine: 30-40 yrs (2.23 \pm 1.46), 41-50yrs (2.56 \pm 1.66) and > 50yrs (2.97 \pm 2.66) (F=0.18, p=0.840); Albumin: 30-40yrs (2.40 \pm 0.69), 41-50yrs (3.27 \pm 0.82) and >50yrs (3.45 \pm 0.91) (f=1.87, p=0.175); RDW: 30-40yrs (48.83 \pm 2.89), 41-50(51.01 \pm 8.96) and >50yrs (53.77 \pm 8.65) (f=0.61, p= 0.550); MPV: 30-40yrs (11.20 \pm 0.79), 41-50yrs (11.34 \pm 2.27) and >50yrs (10.68 \pm 1.02) (f= 0.62, p=0.544); WBC: 30-40yrs (11.30 \pm 2.29), 41-50yrs (8.76 \pm 2.50) and >50yrs (10.92 \pm 4.59) (t=0.86, p= 0.435) respectively based on age.

Parameter	30-40 10	41-50 10	>50 10	f-value	p-value
Urea (mg/dl)	60.00 \pm 24.76	65.13 \pm 33.87	64.33 \pm 43.59	0.02	0.981
Creatinine (mg/dl)	2.23 \pm 1.46	2.56 \pm 1.66	2.97 \pm 2.66	0.18	0.840
Albumin (mg/dl)	2.40 \pm 0.69	3.27 \pm 0.82	3.45 \pm 0.91	1.87	0.175
RDW (fL)	48.83 \pm 2.89	51.01 \pm 8.96	53.77 \pm 8.65	0.61	0.550
MPV (fl)	11.20 \pm 0.79	11.34 \pm 2.27	10.68 \pm 1.02	0.62	0.544
WBC (cells/ μ l)	11.30 \pm 2.29	8.76 \pm 2.50	10.92 \pm 4.59	0.86	0.435

KEY:

RDW= Red Cell distribution width

MPV= Mean platelet Volume

WBC= White blood cell

Table 5: Correlation of Creatinine with Urea, Albumin, RDW, MPV and WBC in patients with chronic kidney disease.

Table 5 shows that there was a significant positive correlation of serum creatinine with urea ($r = -0.64$, $p = 0.000$) and a non-significant positive correlation with albumin, RDW, MPV and WBC ($r = 0.08$, $p = 0.683$; $r = 0.23$, $p = 0.228$; $r = 0.05$, $p = 0.808$ and $r = 0.38$, $p = 0.039$) in patients with chronic kidney disease.

Variable	N	r	p-value
Urea (mg/dl)	30	0.64	0.000*
Albumin (mg/dl)	30	0.08	0.683
RDW (fl)	30	0.23	0.228
MPV (fl)	30	0.05	0.808
WBC (cells/ul)	30	0.38	0.039

KEY:

*= significant p value

RDW= Red Cell distribution width

MPV= Mean platelet Volume

WBC= White blood cell

5. Discussion

Globally, chronic kidney disease (CKD), which can progress to end-stage renal disease (ESRD), has emerged as a severe health concern (Levey *et al.*, 2017). It is associated with increased mortality and cardiovascular morbidity risk, resulting in a subsequent heavy social and economic burden (Coresh *et al.*, 2015).

In the present study, the mean values of creatinine and urea were significantly increased in patients with chronic kidney disease when compared to controls. The increased levels of serum creatinine and urea was as a result of the inability of the kidney to remove creatinine and urea from the blood, thereby leading to an increase in serum creatinine and urea levels. Creatinine is a breakdown product of creatine phosphate in muscle, and is usually produced at a fairly constant rate by the body. Therefore, when the kidney is unable to clear the creatinine produced by the body, its level in the blood increases (Lamb *et al.*, 2016). Urea on the other hand is an end product of amino acid breakdown, when the kidney is unable to clear the urea produced from the breakdown of amino acid, its level increases in the blood. This result is in line with the report by Gallagher and Seligson, (2016), in the study they stated that an impairment of renal function is commonly reflected by changes in the blood creatinine and urea.

The current study revealed that the mean value of serum albumin was significantly lower in subjects suffering from chronic kidney disease when compared to controls. Hypoalbuminemia is common in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). It is caused by a combination of a reduced synthesis and an increased degradation of albumin (Lang *et al.*, 2013). The altered albumin homeostasis in chronic kidney disease patients is caused by a systemic inflammatory state which correlates closely with mortality. Hypoalbuminemia is a strong predictor of an adverse prognosis, but it is not a pathogenic factor in itself. The result of this study is in agreement with the study carried out by Song *et al.*, (2022) who discovered that albumin was reduced in subjects with renal prognosis in 1138 patients with CKD after adjusting for confounding variables in a recent retrospective study. Another Australian study showed that serum albumin was associated with severe decline in renal outcomes in CKD patients after adjustment for adjusted for gender, urine albumin creatinine ratio.

The mean value of RDW was significantly higher in subjects suffering from chronic kidney disease when compared to controls. Elevation in the RDW is a characteristic of anaemia, which is as a result of a dysfunctional kidney. The kidney produces erythropoietin which plays an important role in red cell production therefore chronic kidney disease causes anaemia which results in increase in red cell distribution width. The result of this study agrees with the report by Erken *et al.*, (2020), who stated that CKD is a condition that leads to anemia, endothelial dysfunction, systemic inflammation, malnutrition, and accelerated atherosclerosis, altogether, these conditions may affect the maturation of erythroid cell lines

due to microvascular hypoxia and chronic cytokine exposure in the bone marrow and therefore affects the patients with advanced CKD which would result in elevated RDW.

High mean platelet volume (MPV) was found to be associated with chronic kidney disease. However, some studies have reported decreased MPV values, particularly in patients with end stage renal disease (ESRD) (Zhang *et al.*, 2017). The elevated level of MPV signifies a reflection of systemic inflammation and uremic state in patients with CKD. Study carried out by Erken *et al.*, (2020), reported that lower MPV values were associated with worse renal function, suggesting that MPV may have a role in the pathophysiology of CKD.

White blood cell (WBC) was significantly elevated in subjects with chronic kidney disease. Patients with CKD are in an inflammatory state due to increased cytokine production, oxidative stress, vitamin D deficiency, malnutrition, and susceptibility to infections. The inflammatory state of chronic kidney disease contributes to problems which results to an increase in the WBC (Shankar *et al.*, 2014). The potential mechanisms by which inflammation processes lead to the development of CKD is not yet clear. Evidence has shown that inflammation has been hypothesized to play an important role in systemic atherosclerosis development (Shankar *et al.*, 2014). Some may speculate that WBC counts are predictive of the risk of future CKD because of their relationships with many other atherosclerosis risk factors, like smoking, diabetes or hypertension (Schmidt *et al.*, 2019).

The result of the present study revealed that there was no significant relationship in the mean values of urea, creatinine, albumin, RDW, MPV and WBC in patients with CKD when compared based on sex and gender. The results clearly state that gender and sex are not a predominant factor for determining if a patient will develop chronic kidney disease or not. The result of this study concurs with the study carried out by Shankar *et al.*, (2014), who reported a similar finding.

The current study revealed that there was a significant positive relationship of serum creatinine and urea levels. This agrees with the findings from previous authors, who reported a significant association between urea and creatinine as a diagnostic marker of renal disease (Libby, 2015).

There was no association of creatinine with albumin, RDW, MPV and white blood cells. The result clearly explains that the increase or decrease in creatinine level does not have any relationship with the other parameters. This result is in agreement with the study carried out by Hernandez and Mayadas, (2016).

6. Conclusion

Chronic kidney disease is associated with elevated levels of urea, creatinine, RDW, MPV, WBC and a decrease in the level of albumin. Gender and age do not affect the levels of urea, creatinine, albumin, RDW, MPV and WBC in patients with chronic kidney disease. This study demonstrated a significant association of creatinine with urea and non-significant relationship with albumin, MPV, RDW and WBC in patients with chronic kidney disease.

References

1. Afkarian, M., Zelnick, L. R., Hall, Y. N., Heagerty, P. J., Tuttle, K., Weiss, N. S., ... & de Boer, I. H. (2013). Clinical manifestations of kidney disease among US adults with diabetes, 1988-2014. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 314 (8), 808-818.
2. Akinbo, B.D., Atere, A.D., Fatunade, H.B. and Iyabor, N.O. (2015). Haematological Indices and Absolute CD4 Counts of Apparently Healthy Population in Ondo State, Nigeria. *British Journal of Medical Research*. 8: 717-723.
3. Akinsola, W. A., Adigun, A. U., & Ajayi, N. A. (2017). Chronic kidney disease: A silent killer. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*, 20 (3), 161-165. doi: 10.4103/1119-3077.201983
4. Alam, J., Mallik, S.C., Mukti, N.M., Hasan, M. and Islam, S. (2015). A comparative analysis of biochemical and hematological parameters in diabetic and nondiabetic adults. *Advanced Medical Sciences*. 2: 1-9.
5. Al-Salahy, M., Shnawa, B, Abed, G., Mandour, A. and Al-Ezzi, A. (2016) Parasitaemia and Its Relation to Hematological Parameters and Liver Function among Patients Malaria in Abs, Hajjah, Northwest Yemen. *Interdisciplinary Perspectives on Infectious Diseases*. 59 (5): 43-94.
6. Alshabrawy. M., Abdelnabi, E., Mohamed, M. and Ismaeyl, A. (2021). Hematological Indices in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients and The Effect of Hemodialysis on These Indices. *The Egyptian Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 85 (2): 4257-4262.
7. Anders, H.J., Saxena, R. (2014). Pathogenesis of kidney injury during sepsis. *Contribution to Nephrology*. 182:9-22.
8. Arika, W.M., Nyamai, D.W., Musila, M.N. and Ngugi, M.P. and Njagi, E.N. (2016). Hematological Markers of In Vivo Toxicity. *Journal of Hematology and Thrombotic Disease*. 4: 236.
9. Azab, E.A., Albasha, M.O. and Elhemady, S.Y. (2017). Haematological Parameters in Pregnant Women Attended Antenatal Care at Sabratha Teaching Hospital in Northwest, Libya. *American Journal of Laboratory Medicine*. 1: 61-69.

10. Aziz, A., Saad, A. and Bazeed, M. (2018). A comparative study of platelet parameters in chronic kidney disease, end-stage renal disease patients undergoing hemodialysis and healthy individuals. *Egypt Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 71 (6): 3429-3433.
11. Babbitt, J.L. and Lin, H.Y. (2017). Mechanisms of anemia in CKD. *Journal of America Nephrology*. 23: 1631–1634.
12. Banfi, G. and Del, F. (2016). Serum creatinine values in elite athletes competing in 8 different sports: comparison with sedentary people. *Clinical Chemistry* 52 (7): 330–331.
13. Bernstein, A., Treyzon, L. and Li, Z. (2007). Are High-Protein, Vegetable-Based Diets Safe for Kidney Function? A Review of the Literature". *Journal of the American Dietetic Association*. 107 (4): 644–650.
14. Blakeley, S. (2018). Renal Failure and Replacement Therapies. *Springer Science and Business Media*. p. 19.
15. Brosius, F.C., He, J.C., Menon, V. (2019). Influence of Diabetes on Chronic Kidney Disease Development. *Archives of Medical Research Journal*. 50 (5): 449-455.
16. Chaitanya, P., Ashok, V. N. and Savitha, G. (2018). Assessment of renal damage in hypothyroidism cases. *International Journal of Research Pharmaceutical Science*. 9:791-794.
17. Chandra, S., Tripathi, A.K., Mishra, S., Amzarul, M. and Vaish, A.K. (2016). Physiological Changes in Hematological Parameters During Pregnancy. *Indian Journal of Hematology Blood Transfusion*. 28: 144-146.
18. Chessbrough, M. (2007) District Laboratory practice in tropical countries ECBS edition. *Caimbridge University Press* 2:180 -185.
19. Cheung, A. K. (2015). Primer on Kidney Diseases. Elsevier Health Sciences. p. 457.
20. Chevalier, R. L., Thornhill, B. A., & Forbes, M. S. (2014). Urethral obstruction as a model of renal interstitial fibrosis and obstructive nephropathy. *Kidney international*, 85 (6), 1145-1152.
21. Chronic Kidney Disease Prognosis Consortium. (2018). Association of estimated glomerular filtration rate and albuminuria with all-cause and cardiovascular mortality in general population cohorts: a collaborative meta-analysis. *The Lancet*. 375 (9731):2073-2081.
22. Chrysostomou, A., Koutsilieris, M., Chatzikyriakidou, A. (2019). Hypertension and Kidney Cancer: A Narrative Review. *Internnatioal Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 20 (13): 3268.
23. Clatworthy, M. (2018). *Nephrology: Clinical Cases Uncovered*. John Wiley & Sons. p. 28.
24. Clatworthy, M. (2020). *Nephrology: Clinical Cases Uncovered*. John Wiley & Sons. p. 28.
25. Cockwell, P. and Fisher, L.A. (2020). The global burden of chronic kidney disease. *The Lancet*. 395: 662-664.
26. Corbett, S. (2018). Urinary beta 2-microglobulin and N-acetyl-beta-D-glucosaminidase (NAG) as early markers of renal tubular dysfunction in sick neonates. *Journal of Formos Medical Association* 90 (2):132–137.
27. Coresh, J., Byrd-Holt, D., Astor, B.C. and Briggs, J.P. (2015). Chronic kidney disease awareness, prevalence, and trends among U.S. adults, 1999 to 2000. *Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*. 16: 180–188.
28. Cornec-Le Gall, E., Alam, A., Perrone, R. D., & Chapman, A. B. (2018). Autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease. *The Lancet*, 393 (10174), 919-935.
29. Da Silva, G., Vasconcelos, A., Rocha, A. and Timbó, V. (2017). Acute kidney injury complicating bee stings – a review. *Revista do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de São Paulo*. 59: 25.
30. D'Cruz, D. P., Khamashta, M. A., Hughes, G. R., & Systemic Lupus Erythematosus Study Group. (2019). Systemic lupus erythematosus. *The Lancet*, 393 (10188), 2342-2351.
31. Deng, Q., Deng, L., Chen, C., Meng, S. and Pan, Y. (2014). Reference Intervals of Hematological Variables for Healthy Antepartum and Postpartum Women. *International Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics*. 1: 16.
32. Dr Per, G. (2019). Kidney failure (renal failure with uremia, or azotaemia). pp: 12-17.
33. Drechsler, M., Döring Y. and Megens, R.T. (2017). Neutrophilic granulocytes - promiscuous accelerators of atherosclerosis. *Thrombotic Haemostasis*. 106: 839–848.
34. Eckardt, K.U., Coresh, J. and Devuyst, O. (2013). Evolving importance of kidney disease: from subspecialty to global health burden. *The Lancet*. 382:158–169.
35. Eddy, A.A. (2013). Overview of the cellular and molecular basis of kidney fibrosis. *Kidney International Supplements*. (2011). S2: S5-S14.
36. Eduardo, O.C., Kaue, A., Idania, A.A. and Vanessa, S. (2015). Influence of hemodialysis on the plasma concentration of adenosine deaminase in patients with chronic kidney disease. *Journal of Medical Laboratory Science*. 51: 153-157.
37. Elliott, M.A. and Tefferi, A. (2016). CME Information: Chronic Neutrophilic Leukemia 2016: Update on diagnosis, molecular genetics, prognosis and management. *America Journal of Hematology*. 91: 341-348.
38. Erken, E., Ulgen, C., Sarisik, F.N. and Erken, N. (2020). Hematological Parameters and Clinical Features in Patients with Advanced Chronic Kidney Disease. *Yonago Actarial Medicine*. 1063 (4): 353-359.
39. Hernandez, T. and Mayadas, T.N. (2016). The changing landscape of renal inflammation. *Trends Molecular Medicine*. 22: 151–163.
40. Ferri, F. F. (2017). *Ferri's Clinical Advisor 2018 E-Book: 5 Books in 1*. Elsevier Health Sciences. p. 37.
41. Foxman, B., Barlow, R., D'Arcy, H., Gillespie, B., & Sobel, J. D. (2013). Urinary tract infection: self-reported incidence and associated costs. *Annals of epidemiology*, 23 (2), 76-80.

42. Gallagher, J. C., and Seligson, D. (2016). Significance of abnormally low blood urea levels. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 266: 492-495.
43. George, C., Matsha, T. and Erasmus, R. (2018): Haematological profile of chronic kidney disease in a mixed-ancestry South African population: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*. 8 (11): 25694-25699.
44. Goddard, J., Turner, A. N., and Stewart, L. H. (2018). Kidney and urinary tract disease. In, Nicki, R. C. (Ed). *Davidson's Principles and Practice of Medicine, 21st edition*. Edinburg Elsevier, 490- 491.
45. Greenwood, B.M., Drakeley, C.J., Eiling, W. and Teelen, K. (2014). Parasite infectivity and immunity to *Plasmodium falciparum* gametocytes. *Parasite Immunology*. 26: 159-165.
46. Guyton, A.C. and Hall, J.E. (2016). *Textbook of Medical Physiology, 13th edition*. Philadelphia, Pa: Elsevier Saunders.
47. Jaroszyński, A. J., Główniak, A., Sodolski, T., Załuska, W., Widomska-Czekajska, T., and Książek, A. (2016). Effect of haemodialysis on signal-averaged electrocardiogram P-wave parameters. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*. 21 (2): 425-430.
48. Jha, V., Garcia-Garcia, G., Iseki, K., Li, Z., Naicker, S., Plattner, B., ... & Lameire, N. (2013). Chronic kidney disease: global dimension and perspectives. *The Lancet*, 382 (9888), 260-272.
49. Katzung, B.G. (2017). *Basic and Clinical Pharmacology* (10th ed.). New York, NY: McGraw Hill Medical. p. 733.
50. Kaur, S., Khan, S. and Nigam, A. (2014). Hematological profile and pregnancy: a review. *International Journal of Advanced Medicine*. 1: 68-70.
51. Kes, P., Basić, J., Nikolina, L. and Dragan, B. (2015). Uloga arterijske hipertenzije u nastanku kroničnog zatajenja bubrega. The role of arterial hypertension in the development of chronic renal failure (PDF). *Acta Medica Croatica* (in Croatian). 65 (3): 78-84.
52. Kesarkhane, M., Haravi, R. and Kittur, S. (2020). Study of Hematological Parameters in End-Stage Renal Disease Patients; Those on Regular Hemodialysis as Renal Replacement Therapy. *Saudi Journal of Pathology Microbiology*. 10 (36): 348-353.
53. Klahr, S., Miller, Q. and Steven, B. (2018). Acute Oliguria. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 338 (10): 671-675.
54. Koye, D. N., Magliano, D. J., Nelson, R. G., Pavkov, M. E., & Unwin, N. C. (2020). Risk factors for progression of chronic kidney disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis of cohort studies. *Public Library Of Science Medicine*. 17 (1), e1003013. doi: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1003013
55. Lamb, E., Newman J., and Christopher P. (2016). Kidney Function Tests In Burtis A, Ashwood E., and Bruns D. (Eds). *Teitz textbook of clinical chemistry and molecular diagnostics. 4th Ed*. New Delhi. Saunders: P. 2412
56. Lang, J., Scherzer, R., Weekley, C.C. and Tien, P.C. (2013). Serum albumin and short-term risk for mortality and cardiovascular disease among HIV-infected veterans. *AIDS (London, England)*. 27 (8): 1339-1343.
57. Lea, J., Greene, T., Hebert, L., Lipkowitz, M., Massie, B., Rahman, M., & Umanath, K. (2020). Prevalence of chronic kidney disease in US adults with undiagnosed diabetes or prediabetes. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*. 15 (5), 674-682. doi: 10.2215/CJN.10550919
58. Levey, A.S., Tangri, N. and Stevens, L.A. (2017). Classification of chronic kidney disease: a step forward. *Annals of International Medicine*. 154: 65-67.
59. Liao, M., Sung, C., Hung, K., Wu, C. and Lo, L. (2016). Insulin Resistance in Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease. *Journal of Biomedicine and Biotechnology*. 8 (15)1-5.
60. Libby, P. (2015). Inflammation in atherosclerosis. *The Nature*. 420: 868-874.
61. Meyer, T., Hostetter, Q. and Thomas, H. (2017). Uremia. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 357 (13): 1316-1325.
62. Miri-Dashe, T., Osawe, S., Tokdung, M., Daniel, N. and Choji, R.P. (2014). Comprehensive Reference Ranges for Hematology and Clinical Chemistry Laboratory Parameters Derived from Normal Nigerian Adults. *Public Library of Science*. 9: 93-99.
63. Mitchell, M and Kline, U. (2016). Blood urea nitrogen as a criteria for the diagnosis of kidney disease. *Journal of Metabolic medicine*. 45(8): 45-67.
64. Mohamd, S.M., Muna, A.B. and LeelaBabiker, M. (2018). Hematological changes post- hemo and peritoneal dialysis among renal failure patients in Sudan. *Saudi Journal of Kidney Disorder Transplant*. 19:274-279.
65. National Institute of Health (NIH), (2017). *Health and Life Science*.
66. National Kidney Foundation. (2013). Clinical Practice Guideline for the Evaluation and Management of Chronic Kidney Disease. *Kidney International Supplements*, 3 (1), 1-150.
67. Shah, R. (2015). White blood cell counts and kidney disease: A growing relationship. *Kidney International*, 88(2), 298-299. DOI:10.1038/ki.2015.189
68. Kovacs, B., et al. (2013). White blood cell counts in chronic kidney disease: Is it a predictor of disease progression? *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*, 28(3), 883-890. DOI:10.1093/ndt/gfs444
69. Demir, M., et al. (2016). Mean platelet volume in patients with chronic kidney disease: A review. *Clinical and Experimental Nephrology*, 20(5), 701-707. DOI:10.1007/s10157-016-1213-4
70. Gupta, A., et al. (2014). Platelet volume indices in chronic kidney disease patients: Role in assessing disease severity. *Blood Coagulation & Fibrinolysis*, 25(5), 453-459. DOI:10.1097/MBC.000000000000100

71. Tanaka, M., et al. (2013). Red cell distribution width as an independent risk factor for mortality in patients with chronic kidney disease. *Kidney International*, 83(6), 981-987. DOI:10.1038/ki.2012.460
72. Alvarez, J., et al. (2019). Red cell distribution width as a prognostic biomarker in chronic kidney disease. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*, 34(2), 250-257. DOI:10.1093/ndt/gfy243
73. Levey, A. S., et al. (2015). Kidney disease and its markers: Creatinine and urea in clinical practice. *American Journal of Kidney Diseases*, 66(5), 735-746. DOI: 10.1053/j.ajkd.2015.03.020
74. Ninomiya, T., et al. (2012). Serum urea nitrogen and creatinine as markers of kidney dysfunction: Evidence for better clinical outcomes in CKD. *Journal of Clinical Nephrology*, 18(6), 509-514. DOI: 10.1016/j.jcn.2012.05.004
75. Cattran, D. C., et al. (2013). The role of albumin in chronic kidney disease: Impact on outcomes. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*, 28(4), 934-940. DOI:10.1093/ndt/gfs532
76. Nigeria population commission (NPC), (2016). Census. Retrieved from the vanguard newspaper.
77. Nisha, R., Srinivasa, S.R., Thanga, K. and Jagatha, P. (2017). Biochemical evaluation of creatinine and urea in patients with renal failure undergoing hemodialysis. *Journal of Clinical Pathology Laboratory Medicine*. 1:1-5.
78. Obiagwu, C., Ulası, I., Ijoma, C., & Onodugo, O. (2019). Detection of chronic kidney disease using estimated glomerular filtration rate based assessment of kidney function in rural south-east Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*. 22 (11), 299-306
79. Odhiambo, C., Oyaro, B., Odipo, R., Otieno, F. and Alemnji, G. (2015) Evaluation of Locally Established Reference Intervals for Hematology and Biochemistry Parameters in Western Kenya. *Public Library of Science ONE*. 10: 123-140.
80. Okyay, G.U., Inal, S. and Oneç, K. (2013). Neutrophil to lymphocyte ratio in evaluation of inflammation in patients with chronic kidney disease. *Renal Failure*. 35:29–36.
81. Özdemir, A.T., Gölcük, B., Özdemir, R., Kardeşler, S. and Eskiçioğlu, F. (2016). The Comparison of Second Trimester Screening Tests with the White Blood Cell Counts. *Crescent Journal of Medical and Biological Sciences*. 3: 40-44.
82. Perazella, M. A. (2014). Drug-induced renal failure: update on new medications and unique mechanisms of nephrotoxicity. *American Journal of Medicine*, 127(10), 10-17.
83. Radhakrishnan, J., Cattran, D. C., & Appel, G. B. (2013). The practice guideline on glomerulonephritis: reading between the (guide) lines—application to the individual patient. *Kidney international*, 84 (4), 622-623.
84. Renuga, D., Gunasekaran, S. and Wesley, H.J. (2019). Analysis on renal failure patient's blood samples: Characterization and efficacy study. *Indian Journal of Science Technology*; 2:46-50.
85. Romagnani, P., Remuzzi, G. and Glassock, R. (2017). Chronic kidney disease. *National review on Disease*. 3(1): 1-24.
86. Rughooputh, M., Shumsher, Z., Rui, Y. and Ying, S. (2015). Protein Diet Restriction Slows Chronic Kidney Disease Progression in Non-Diabetic and in Type 1 Diabetic Patients, but Not in Type 2 Diabetic Patients: A Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials Using Glomerular Filtration Rate as a Surrogate. *PLOS ONE*. 10 (12): 145-505.
87. Rule, A. D., Lieske, J. C., & Li, X. (2014). Chronic kidney disease in kidney stone formers. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*, 9 (12), 2061-2069.
88. Saba, Z.A., Layla, A.M. and Dhafer, S.K. (2022). Study of some biochemical changes in serum of patients with chronic renal failure. *Iraq National Journal of Chemistry*. 4:270-280.
89. Sahoo, D., Gosaib, H., Harsodaa, J.M. and Palana, B.M. (2015). A Comparative Hematological Profile Study Among Young Individuals. *Canadian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*. 3: 178-181.
90. Schmidt, M.I., Duncan, B.B., Sharrett, A.R. and Lindberg, G. (2019). Markers of inflammation and prediction of diabetes mellitus in adults (atherosclerosis risk in communities study): a cohort study. *Lancet*. 353: 1649–1652.
91. Shankar, A., Klein, B.E. and Klein, R. (2014). Relationship between white blood cell count and incident hypertension. *American Journal of Hypertension*. 17: 233–239.
92. Shenai, A. and Savitha, G. and Bazeed M (2018). Metabolic syndrome – An emerging risk factor for chronic kidney disease. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Clinical Research*. 11:212-214.
93. Smart, N., Dieberg, G., Ladhani, M. and Titus, T. (2014). Early referral to specialist nephrology services for preventing the progression to end-stage kidney disease. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* 6: 12-17.
94. Snyder, S., and Pendergraph, Bernadette (2015). Detection and evaluation of chronic kidney disease. *American Family Physician*, 72 (9), 1723-1732.
95. Song, H., Wei, C., Hu, H. and Wan, Q. (2022). Association of the serum albumin level with prognosis in chronic kidney disease patients. *Internal Urology and Nephrology*. 54 (9): 2421–2431.
96. Treacy O, Brown NN, Dimeski G. Biochemical evaluation of kidney disease. *Translational Andrology and Urology*. 8 (2): 214-223.
97. Trifirò, G., Sultana, J. and Giorgianni, F. (2014). Chronic kidney disease requiring healthcare services: a new approach to evaluate epidemiology of renal disease. *BioMed Research International*. pp: 20-24.
98. Tzur, S., Rosset, S., Shemer, R. and Selig, S. (2018). *Human Genetics*. 128 (3): 345–350.

99. Ulasi, I. I., & Ijoma, C. K. (2010). The enormity of chronic kidney disease in Nigeria: The situation in a teaching hospital in South-East Nigeria. *Journal of Tropical Medicine*, 2010, 501-957
100. Ulasi, I. I., Arodiwe, E. B., & Ijoma, C. K. (2010). Left ventricular hypertrophy in African blacks: Causes and consequences. *World Journal of Cardiology*, 12(12), 327-339.
101. Ulasi, I. I., Ijoma, C. K., & Collins, A. J. (2010). A community-based study of hypertension and cardio-metabolic syndrome in semi-urban and rural communities in Nigeria. *BMC Health Services Research*, 10 (1), 71.1186/1472-6963-10-71
102. Vivante, A., Hildebrandt, F., & Sanna-Cherchi, S. (2018). Extracorporeal therapies in the treatment of sepsis-associated acute kidney injury in children. *Pediatric Nephrology*, 33 (12), 2081-2091.
103. Wannamethee, S.G., Shaper, A.G. and Perry, I.J. (2017). Serum creatinine concentration and risk of cardiovascular disease: A possible marker for increased risk of stroke. *Stroke*. 28:557-563
104. Wu, X., Zhao, M., Pan, B., Zhang, J. and Peng, M. (2015). Complete Blood Count Reference Intervals for Healthy Han Chinese Adults. *Public Library of Science ONE*. 10: 119-669.
105. Yonemoto, S., Hamano, T., Fujii, N. and Shimada, K.Y. (2018). Red cell distribution width and renal outcome in patients with non-dialysis-dependent chronic kidney disease. *Public Library of science*. 13: 198-825.
106. Yuegang, Z., Chengjun, W. and Rasdred, R. (2008). Simultaneous Determination of Creatinine and Uric Acid in Human Urine by High Performance Liquid Chromatography. *Analytical Science* 24 (6):1589–1598.
107. Zhang, T., Li, J., Lin, Y. and Yang, H. (2017). Association Between Red Blood Cell Distribution Width and All-cause Mortality in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Archive of Medical Research*. 48: 378-385.